

SEARCHING FOR INSPIRATION DURING IDEA GENERATION

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ABSTRACT

When facing a design problem, both novice and expert designers tend to rely on a variety of available sources to get inspired during idea generation. Therefore, searching for and collecting diverse stimuli during the early phases of the design process is considered a well-known practice amongst designers. Despite this general assumption, there is no clear empirical evidence on how novice or expert practitioners get inspired, their preferences on various material sources, or how they value such potential resources. A questionnaire for novice and expert designers was developed in order to better understand these issues. The findings indicate that novices and experts alike tend to look for existing design solutions that resemble the problem(s) at hand, potentially neglecting more abstract and distant information. The results suggest that the designers in this survey show a tendency to not fully explore a number of available resources, ultimately leading to hindrances in their creative processes. Further results of this study uncover interesting information strategies of designers which should be considered when developing creative approaches in design education.

Keywords: Sources of inspiration, external stimuli, novice and expert designers

INTRODUCTION

It is widely recognised that designers, independently of the task at hand or their level of expertise, seek different kinds of support while designing (Goldschmidt and Smolkov, 2006). The type of support designers search encompasses a large variety of internal (e.g. memories) and external (e.g. images and text) stimuli. Furthermore, there is a variety of

methods which aim to support the designers' creativity (Higgins, 2005), focusing on diverse purposes and inspirational sources, which can influence designers in an unconscious, accidental or deliberate manner (Goldschmidt and Sever, 2010). Designers can actively engage in inspiration search, normally in specific opportune moments, but any stimulus can become relevant to a given design problem, at any time. Inspirational sources have, therefore, a ubiquitous value (Eckert and Stacey, 2000). As a result, the generation of creative ideas is largely based on the influence of different kinds of stimuli that designers search for or end up interacting with. Moreover, it is well accepted both in design education and professional practice that sources of inspiration can stretch the solution space and enlarge the potential pool of creative solutions (e.g. Goldschmidt and Sever, 2010). Nevertheless, many researchers have turned their attention to the potential negative impact external stimuli might have in creative design activities. A number of empirical studies have shown how the use of external stimuli could constrain creativity, often leading to, for instance, design fixation (Jansson and Smith, 1991; Purcell and Gero, 1996).

Despite such controversial findings regarding the influence of external stimuli, there is still a lack of empirical data on the subject of sources of inspiration in design. Here we will focus on two main questions about inspirational sources that need further investigation: 1. What do designers from different levels of expertise search for when trying to extend their solution space? And 2. How do external stimuli influence and shape the generation of creative solution ideas?

The present paper is based on a study which addresses the first question. Knowing in detail what novice and expert designers use as sources for

inspiration is an essential step to start understanding how the idea generation process takes place.

In order to address these issues, we developed and conducted a questionnaire on novice and expert designers' self-reported preferences, thoughts and attitudes regarding inspirational sources and ideation methods used in the early phases of the design process. A better understanding of what distinguishes novice from expert designers, on their preferences for sources of inspiration, can be a valuable outcome for design education and creativity research.

The present paper starts off by briefly reviewing research undertaken on the topic of sources of inspiration, design methods and creativity, followed by a description of the setup of the study we conducted. Further on, we present and discuss the results from our survey based on the statistical analysis, and a discussion concerning on how novice and expert designers deal with sources of inspiration while they are designing. Concluding remarks and recommendations for further research complete this paper.

SOURCES OF INSPIRATION

Throughout their education and professional life, designers learn how to grasp what is around them and find inspiration in literally almost everything (Eckert, Stacey and Earl, 2005). The array of possible sources of inspiration can vary across different categories from internal to external stimuli, the former being composed by mental imagery and verbal information, for instance. The latter can be further divided into pictorial, verbal, sound or three-dimensional stimuli (Eastman, 2001). The prominent role given to inspiration search can be explained by a number of reasons:

- to stimulate creativity and arouse a strategic breakthrough throughout the creative process;
- to support awareness about previous solutions;
- to create the appropriate frame of reference to new innovate designs;
- to share knowledge with other stakeholders;
- to facilitate and accelerate the idea generation process (e.g., Eckert and Stacey, 2000)

Whilst searching for inspiration, designers tend to collect physical and/or mental visual samples (Keller

et al, 2008), which can trigger possible ideas and be later retrieved to solve problems.

Despite the large amount of different stimuli available, designers tend to prefer pictorial examples over textual or three-dimensional representations (Gonçalves, Cardoso and Badke-Schaub, 2011). When questioned about their preference regarding the use of visual, textual or three-dimensional stimuli during idea generation, novice and expert designers indicated images as the preferred inspirational source. Images can, indeed, provide straightforward and intuitive cues that do not require translation between different perceptual modalities (Malaga, 2000). Hence, images are a fast and economic way to stimulate the generation of combined ideas. Moreover, designers are commonly considered as visualizers, due to their tendency to convey and understand messages through images, while designing (Mednick, 1962; Cai, Do and Zimring, 2010).

The use of visual stimuli in problem solving has been widely discussed in several fields. Malaga (2000), for instance, reports on an experiment where participants had to generate ideas for ill-defined problems, while being exposed to textual, pictorial or a textual-pictorial stimuli combination. In such studies, exposure to visual stimuli (either images alone or the combination of images and text) prompted the participants to generate significantly more creative ideas than the other conditions. These results led Malaga (2000) to believe that *word* stimuli might contribute to functional fixedness (Maier, 1931), a behaviour whereby people can only visualize the most familiar functions of an object, making it very difficult to think of other uses for that same object.

On another study, Casakin (2005) demonstrated that a rich collection of visual representations, both from within and between domains related to the problem being addressed, could help novice and expert designers when dealing with ill-defined problems. In such study, which focused on the influence of analogies during idea generation, the quality of the solutions generated by the participants was enhanced when a diversified number of images were made available to them. Designers participating in that study were stimulated by such visual analogs even when they were not explicitly instructed to use

analogic reasoning to solve the problem. Contrary to these findings on the positive effect of visual stimuli, earlier research studies have shown that existing examples could have an unproductive influence on the generation of creative ideas (e.g., Purcell and Gero, 1996; Jansson and Smith, 1991). These limitations towards originality as one parameter of creativity have been termed design fixation - i.e., an unconscious tendency to reuse parts/principles of previously seen examples during idea generation (Jansson and Smith, 1991). Following the results of the different studies, whilst some visual stimuli can enhance creativity, precedent images can also structure mental representation in such a way that the ideas are incorporated into the new design with non-creative results (Perttula and Liikkanen, 2006). Despite the dominant presence of visual stimuli, and regardless of their ambiguous effect, there are reasons to assume that other representational stimuli could also be influential for the generation of creative solutions. Goldschmidt and Sever (2010) have shown the positive influence of using text as stimuli during idea generation in terms of originality, when compared to conditions that did not receive any external stimuli.

In conclusion, previous research has brought forward a considerable amount of ambiguous results stating that the same representation modality can incite as well as hinder design creativity. Ultimately, enhancing creativity might not only depend on the form kind of the representation utilised, but also on what it tries to convey.

CREATING NEW IDEAS

A new idea does not appear from thin air. At first, a designer relies on the problem definition which will eventually lead to an understanding of the problem, what then might deliver a first mental model of the problem space. Secondly, the designer analyses the context of the problem, trying to explore what is known and what can be improved. A list of requirements is assessed and (ideally) constantly verified, but it is also necessary to investigate what has been done before to solve the same or similar problems. For instance, the exploration of competitor products can be identified as a main inspirational search, which does not only provide information about possible restrictions (such as

existing patents), but can also lead to new ideas, for example, when it is needed to circumvent the existing patent. Undoubtedly, the most common behaviour of the designer is the act of seeking inspiration within the design problem field but also in more distant or non-related areas. The phase of idea generation, as any stage of the design process, is highly iterative and presumes changes of direction. Regardless of how novel and unexplored a problem is, designers always use their previous knowledge to understand and define the problem and to generate ideas.

Generally speaking, the way we approach a new situation is directed by prevailing cognitive structures that help us to perceive and understand what exists around us. We rely on concepts (mental models) to discover and structure the unknown (Badke-Schaub et al., 2007). Likewise, new knowledge is based on accumulated models of past experience and concepts, because new information is always related to the categories that exist already. For instance, we do not have to analyse each single example of a door to know how it is supposed to work; one just needs to relate the newly encountered door and compare it with similar objects in the related categories (Murphy, 2002). Hence, also new ideas are based on existing knowledge. In the book 'Displacement of concepts', Schön (1963) explores the topic of concept formation, where he developed the theory of 'generative metaphors'. According to Schön, generative metaphors provide a frame of reflection, which enables us to build intuitively and implicitly new knowledge based on the old. However, existing information is not merely reused when new circumstances are presented. Instead, a *transformation* is needed and new meaning is created from the relation between the known and unknown, according to the new setting. In other words, novel ideas can be generated when, within new situations, old concepts are brought into different perspectives, triggering new interpretations. The process of displacement has four non-sequential but dependent phases: transposition (where an old concept is transferred to a new setting only as a symbol), interpretation (when partial transferred symbols need adaptation to fit within new settings), correction (to detach old

concept symbols from previous framework) and spelling out (an evaluation moment between the old and new concept). This theory offers a possible explanation of how new ideas are created through the displacement of old concepts from known settings.

Based on the idea that cognitive processes in design are characterized by a precedent-based reasoning, Oxman and Oxman (1992) postulate two cognitive styles in design: refinement and adaptation. While during refinement new knowledge is generated by the substitution of abstract previous representations to more specific ones; during adaptation, precedent knowledge is transformed to the new situation, whereby interpretation takes an important role. Obviously, there seems to be a common agreement that some of the most important sources for the generation of new ideas are knowledge and experience of the designer with previous design solutions (Pasman, 2003; Eckert et al, 2005). The way how the “relevant knowledge” is addressed to elicit the creation of new ideas can be answered by the assumptions of the associative theory of creative thinking (Mednick, 1962). Mednick defines creative thinking as “the forming of associative elements into new combinations which either meet specified requirements or are in some way useful” (1962, p.221). According to Mednick, three processes are the source of the generation of creative ideas: serendipity, mediation and similarity. The way in which one categorises ideas and concepts, determines how associations are created, which leads to more or less creative ideas. Thus, if a higher number of associations is evoked, the probability of creative ideas can also increase.

Nevertheless, associations are not always continually evoked and there might also occur counter-intuitive associations. In fact, each new situation (or design problem) can be described by structural components and the relations between them. These system structures provide information on which there are categories that might be of further relevance in order to solve the design problem (Schön, 1963). Accordingly, the identification of the problem belonging to a specific category can lead to the activation of cognitive processes, which can obstruct access to other categories that require higher levels of abstraction. Thus, in order to promote access to a

higher level of abstraction, it is important to consider how design problems are stated and from which categories the inspiration derives.

RESEARCH STUDY

A questionnaire (using NetQ software (NetQuestionnaires Nederland BV) was developed to find out the preferences of designers for different inspiration material. Our aim was to primarily understand which kind of stimuli is used as source of inspiration during creative design processes, depending from the knowledge of the designers. Additionally, we considered that this knowledge would be essential to understand how new ideas are structured. Thus, the questionnaires were given to 103 industrial design engineering master students (i.e., novice designers) from the Faculty of Industrial Design Engineering (Delft University of Technology, The Netherlands) and 52 professional designers (i.e., expert designers), mainly from The Netherlands and Portugal. The questionnaire, which took on average 15 minutes to be filled in, could be completed online or on paper, according to the participants' preferences. Most of the items of the questionnaire were scaled on a 5-point Likert scale (e.g. 1 = never; 2 = rarely; 3 = sometimes; 4 = often; 5 = always), but also yes/no questions and multiple choices were included. In order to further clarify some of the issues addressed, participants were asked to answer additional open-ended questions.

In total, the questionnaire was structured in five sections:

- Section 1: Background information on the participants;
- Section 2: Representation stimuli and sources of inspiration;
- Section 3: Ideation methods;
- Section 4: Reflection on the design process;
- Section 5: Design teams.

The present paper places emphasis on section 2 of the questionnaire. The remaining topics covered by the questionnaire are discussed elsewhere (Gonçalves, Cardoso and Badke-Schaub, 2011). Section 2 of the questionnaire asked about the material sources that novice and expert designers favour during conceptual phases, and how often they

use them. A list of sources of inspiration was obtained from informal talks with designers from different backgrounds, as well as from the literature. A total of 27 possible material sources were gathered and clustered into three initial categories:

- Sources of information: Design magazines; Design books; Newspapers; Magazines from other fields; Internet; Art; Competitor products; Other designers; Previous personal projects; Memories (past experiences); Nature; Places.
- Physical properties: Shapes; Colours; Materials; Textures; Product functionality.
- Activities: Walking around; Listening to music; Watching movies; Taking a bath/shower; Talking to people; Sleeping; Doing sports; Going to museums; In the bathroom; Reading.

In addition to these material sources, participants could add other options not included in the questionnaire.

DATA ANALYSIS

The analysis of the questionnaire is divided into two parts. Whilst in a first part we analyse the topic of inspiration value, in a second part, we concentrate our attention on designers' preferences for different material sources. Each part is examined through a *within-group and between-group analysis*: the former analysis deals with the individual responses within each group (novices as one group separate from experts as another group), using a one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and Pearson Correlation Coefficient; the latter analysis compares novices' responses against those provided by the experts, for which we used an Independent-Samples T-test.

RESULTS

The following sections present the results from the questionnaires, and we start with some more general considerations of the participants on the topic.

SEARCHING FOR INSPIRATION: GENERAL IMPORTANCE, FREQUENCY OF USE AND MOMENT OF HIGHEST IMPORTANCE

In this section we present the results of how much novice and expert designers appreciate inspiration,

when they search for it and how much they actually use inspiration while designing.

Within-group analysis: novices and experts

The results reveal that inspiration search is considered *very important* for both novice and expert designers in order to continue with the generation of ideas ($x = 4.39$ and $x = 4.44$, respectively - Figure 1 left, in which 5 corresponds to *Very Important* and 1 corresponds to *Not at all important*).

Figure 1. Left - Novices and Experts: importance of inspiration; Right - Novices and Experts: Inspiration's frequency of use.

Therefore, the expert and novice designers from our sample entrust an enormous value to inspirational search.

Equally, the same similarity of results can be found regarding novices and expert designers' frequency of searching for inspiration, with both groups reporting on regularly engaging in such activity ($x = 4.17$ and $x = 4.33$, respectively - Figure 1 right, in which 5 refers to *Always* and 1 to *Never*).

Answering the question "*when is inspiration most important for designers*", participants could choose between several options: *all the time; once I get the brief; during problem analysis; during idea generation; during conceptual design; during embodiment and detail design; in discussion with co-workers; in discussion with clients*. With this array of options, we intended to obtain a broad overview of the designers' considerations on the design process, trying to map all the important phases for the generation of a design idea. Nevertheless, the majority of the novices and experts expresses a preference for searching for inspiration specifically

during *idea generation*, which is significantly more often selected than any other option (Figure 2, $p < 0.05$ and Figure 3, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 2. Novices: when is inspiration important.

Figure 3. Experts: when is inspiration important.

Between-group analysis: novices and experts

As mentioned before, novices and experts alike report crediting a high value to inspiration during the design process (Figure 1 left) and their frequent use of sources of inspiration during the design process (Figure 1 right).

Regarding the *most opportune moment* to search for inspiration, once more there are no differences between the responses provided by the novices and experts.

PREFERENCES FOR MATERIAL SOURCES

In the following section, we look at novice and expert designers' preferences for particular material stimuli.

Within-group analysis: novices and experts' preferences for different sources of information

When analysing the preferences on material sources, especially focusing on *sources of information*, novices report a substantial preference to concentrate their inspiration search on the *Internet*. This preference presents significant differences in relation to all the other material sources listed in the questionnaire (Figure 4, $p < 0.05$). Looking at *competitor products* and retrieving inspiration from *personal memories* are the second and third most important sources of information (but still, significantly lower than using the *Internet*). Conversely, *newspapers, magazines from other fields and places*, are novices' least preferred sources of information.

Experts' preferences on material sources are similar to those of novices. *Internet, competitor products* and *memories* are also reported by the experts as the most preferred sources.

On the other hand, *places, magazines from other fields and newspapers* are the least preferred ones by experts.

In fact, whilst novices choose searching for information on the *Internet* much more frequent than in any other material source, this is not true for experts. Experts do not show a significant difference between *Internet* and *competitor products* or between *Internet* and *memories*. In fact, experts rate the item '*competitor products*' as almost as important as browsing the *Internet*. This specific material source is significantly different from all other means of obtaining inspiration covered by the questionnaire.

From these results, we were interested in a more thorough examination of the kind of material sources designers search for. As it was shown earlier in this

related. A Pearson's Chi Square test was used to test the differences between the aforementioned categories, however, yielding no significant

Figure 4. Novices (Left) and Experts' (Right) preferences for sources of information.

paper, *Internet*, *competitor products* and *memories* are the most frequently chosen material sources by novice and expert designers.

differences between them. Hence, we can not verify whether these designers are indeed preferring design related stimuli over other distant stimuli, not directly related with design.

Another interesting result is that designers seem to value design related stimuli much more than searching for inspiration in distant areas. In order to analyse this, a categorisation of the material sources used in this questionnaire was made and the 27 stimuli covered by the questionnaire were grouped into four categories: Design related; Non-Design related; Memory related and Cognitive Distance

Within-group analysis: novices and experts' preferences for activities

As stated before, the results show that novice and expert designers tend to have the same preferences for specific activities when searching for inspiration, the most preferred ones being: *talking to people*,

Figure 5. Novices' (Left) and Experts' (Right) preferences for activities.

walking around, reading and listening to music. When we examine the results from the novices in detail, we see that *talking to people* is the most preferred stimulus for searching for inspiration, significantly more than any other activity (Figure 5 left, $p < 0.05$)

Unlike novices, experts seem to share their preference between two activities, when trying to find inspiration. Whereas *talking to people* is evidently the most chosen activity, it is not significantly more frequent than *walking around*. Nevertheless, the activity *talking to people* is significantly higher in relation to the remaining eight stimuli (Figure 5 right, $p < 0.05$). On the other hand, *walking around* was considered significantly more stimulating than the least preferred five activities (Figure 5 right, $p < 0.05$).

Within-group analysis: novices and experts' preferences for physical properties

When focusing on physical properties of examples, novices highlight shape, *product functionality* and *material* as the most important features for inspiration. Out of these properties a significantly higher preference for *colours* and *textures can be derived* (Figure 6 left, $p < 0.05$).

Figure 6. Novices' (Left) and Experts' (Right) preferences for physical properties.

In contrast to novices, experts give more importance to *product functionality*, as well as to *material* and *shape* when looking for inspiration in existing examples. Nevertheless, *product functionality* is only

significantly higher in relation to *textures*, the least chosen stimuli (Figure 6 right, $p < 0.05$).

Between-group analysis: novices' and experts' preferences for material sources

Across all three categories of material sources - *Sources of information*; *Physical Properties*; and *Activities* - results show that novice and expert designers seem to choose a rather similar range of stimuli.

Within-group analysis: correlation between preferences for material sources and representational stimuli

The results reveal that novice designers manifest a preference for *images* when looking for inspiration, preferring to look for these in *design books*, as well as in the work of *other designers*. In terms of the category *physical properties*, novices give special attention to *shapes* and *colours* of pictorial examples (table 1).

		Novices		
		Images	Objects	Text
+	Colours * *		Going to museums * *	Newspapers * *
	Design books *		Newspapers *	Reading * *
-	Other designers *		Places *	Doing sports *
	Shapes *		Walk around *	Going to museums *
-		—	—	Shapes *
				Materials *

Table 1. Novices: correlation between representation stimuli and material sources (* * corresponds to $p < 0.01$ and * corresponds to $p < 0.05$).

When expert designers use *images* as their preferred type of representational stimuli, they tend to look in magazines from different fields and engage in activities such as *watching movies* and *visiting museums*. Conversely, these designers also tend to talk less with *other people*, when seeking for inspiration, and rarely look into examples of *competitor products* (Table 2).

Regarding designers' preference for *objects*, novice designers who prefer objects as triggers for inspiration report a tendency to engage in activities that enable them to interact with such physical examples, for instance: getting inspired by *places*; *walking around*; and *visiting museums*. There is also a positive correlation between novices' preference

Experts			
	Images	Objects	Text
+	Magazines other fields * Watching movies * Going to museums *	Materials ** Competitor products * Other designers *	—
-	Talking to people * Competitor products *	—	Competitor products ** Product functionality *

Table 2. Experts: correlation between representation stimuli and material sources (** corresponds to $p < 0.01$ and * corresponds to $p < 0.05$).

for *objects* and choosing to look for inspiration in *newspapers*. Experts giving preference to these representational stimuli also prefer to inspire themselves by looking at *competitor products* and other *designers' portfolio*. This represents a highly significant correlation between their preference for *objects* and choosing materiality as the most relevant physical property of inspirational examples.

On the subject of preferences for textual representation, there are negative correlations between the use of *text* and looking into *other products* from the market and *product functionality* as physical property. Therefore, experts preferring to use textual stimuli representations do not look for inspiration in *competitor products* nor in *product functionality*.

On the other hand, novice designers preferring to use *text* over other representational stimuli, indicate a similar preference for searching for inspiration in *newspapers* and engaging in activities such as *going to museums*, *reading* and, curiously, *doing sports*. Furthermore, regarding novices' preference for physical properties of objects, such as *shapes* and *material*, these are negatively correlated with their preference for *text*.

More experienced designers claim not using *text* as much as they use *objects* and *images* when searching for inspiration. Therefore, there are no positive correlations between their preferences for *text* and other material sources.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

VALUE OF INSPIRATION

The results presented in this paper confirm what the majority of designers may already know but that

previous research has not been explicit about: searching for inspiration is a highly valued activity and it happens frequently (and almost exclusively) during design idea generation, regardless of designers' level of expertise. Our results indicate that, both novice and experts value inspiration. These results reassure the importance of investigating the topic of sources of inspiration within the area of design creativity. Our participants rely on inspiration on a daily basis and can potentially be affected - positively or negatively, by diverse stimuli presented in different forms and comprising different content.

MATERIAL SOURCES - SOURCES OF INFORMATION

Interestingly, two of the most preferred sources of information can be considered *design-related*, i.e., examples of *competitive products* or similar solutions for the same design problem on *Internet*. Nevertheless, it is important to consider that the selected stimuli used in this survey vary in terms of specificity. For instance, whilst *competitive products* as source of information, refer to a well-defined category of design examples, *Internet* is much more general. In fact, we have no clear indication of what designers search for when they are browsing the Internet. Nevertheless, our assumption also from interviews with designers is that, especially in an initial phase, designers look for existing design solutions or problem related information, which then places *Internet* as a design-related content stimulus. As it was described previously in this paper, research on design fixation has demonstrated that the use of priming examples as stimuli can result in counterproductive behaviour. One of such situations is the inadvertent repetition of parts/principles of the seen examples, which can be a hindrance in creativity (e.g., Jansson and Smith, 1991). For that reason, we can speculate that if designers have a tendency to become too dependent on design-related stimuli they, consequently, increase the probability of design fixation occurring. Whilst on one hand, students and practitioners seem to be hijacking their own creativity; on the other hand, there are reasons that justify this behaviour. Design-related stimuli, such as competitive products and iconic design objects, are easily accessible, both physically (through pictorial examples on the

Internet, for instance) and cognitively (part of the designers' mental collection of cases). Moreover, local analogies (or within domain) are easier to evoke, as they share a higher level of similarity between source and target problem (Christensen and Schunn, 2007). Consequently, distant analogies, which are aroused by between domain sources (such as more abstract, as well as distant related stimuli) can be rather difficult to evoke. However, designers are known to be skilled in establishing distant analogies (Casakin, 2003). Under typical time and budget limitations, the designers taking part in our survey show a tendency to employ strategies of cognitive economy (e.g., Pasman, 2003) and conform themselves by searching for the most immediate sources of inspiration. This is what seems to happen when novice and expert designers report that they search for inspiration on the *Internet* and when looking at *competitor products*. Furthermore, the third most used stimulus for both levels of expertise is their own *memory*. This fact is congruent with the findings that designers rely on their own past experiences and knowledge of previous cases to find inspiration and to develop new ideas and concepts (Oxman, 1990). Also, experts in our study report to frequently search for memory-related stimuli: they indicate looking for inspiration within their own *memory* (57%) and *previous personal projects* (55%). This result is consistent with empirical studies that demonstrate that experts are much quicker in generation of ideas because they use cases stored in their memory as basis for new ideas.

On the other hand, novices also report that they refer to *memory* when designing (58%), but they less often retrieve information from *previous personal projects* (41%).

It is easily understandable why novices seem to not use *previous personal projects*, as their design knowledge is still limited. *Memories* and *previous personal projects* are still important for novices; however, the amount of information in the required field of knowledge is probably smaller.

In summary, these results demonstrate that designers, especially experts, are able to apply a memory-based reasoning to stimulate creativity (Oxman, 1990).

In line with that explanation can be seen also the prominence *Internet* seems to have for novice

designers' preferences for material sources. Whilst experts choose three stimuli as the highest-ranking (*Internet*, *competitor products* and *memories*), novices indicate *Internet* as significantly more important than all the other stimuli. This result may indicate that novice designers choose the most readily available external stimulus compared to experts, who rely on their bigger pool of internal stimuli available.

MATERIAL SOURCES - ACTIVITIES

During idea generation, it is usually expected that if designers get stuck, they might attempt to engage in certain activities that may overcome their current block. There are empirical studies that examined the role of incubation as a way to support creativity during problem solving (e.g., Wallas, 1926; Ellwood et al., 2009). Incubation breaks are acknowledged as periods where "doing nothing which relates to the problem" will help the brain activities to restructure and by this gaining new ideas or even a solution for the problem.

We were interested in investigating which kind of activities are the most preferred by designers, in order to stimulate the generation of creative ideas. According to our findings, the most preferred activity by both experts and novices is *talking to people*.

Therefore, it seems that it is essential for designers to share their design problems with peers and outsiders, who may not be in the same mindset as they are. Additionally, explaining the problem to colleagues, specialists on the topic or even people naïve to design, can help designers to restructure the problem and to get a new view on the problem.

Whilst *talking to people* could potentially promote to unblock the designer, it does not correspond exactly to the definition of incubation break. The incubation process is assumed to be non-conscious (Ellwood et al., 2009), which differs from *talking to people* specifically about the problem at hand.

All the other activities also covered by the questionnaire are rated by novices as less important than *talking to people*. However, the activities *walking around*, *reading* and *listening to music* can be considered as incubation facilitating activities. They may lead to a distance to the problem and thus may result in a new view on the problem.

Novice designers rated these activities as much less important, compared to *talking to people*. Expert designers, however, consider *walking around* as an important activity in order to stimulate the creation of ideas. Discussing a problem with other persons often provides immediate responses that may or may not lead to creative solutions, at least increasing the feeling of getting closer to a solution.

MATERIAL SOURCES - PHYSICAL PROPERTIES

The findings indicate that novices and experts value different physical properties of stimuli when searching for inspiration. Novice designers concentrate more importance on superficial features, given by the immediate encounter with example solutions. Expert designers, in contrast, tend to give more attention to functional principles of existing solutions, which can be used as base for new ideas.

As it was referred before, new creative ideas can be generated through a precedent-based reasoning, for instance (Oxman and Oxman, 1992). However, the results presented here seem to indicate that novice designers are mainly focusing on superficial features, such as shapes of existing objects. Whilst shape can be an useful physical feature for inspiration of creative ideas, its ill-judged use can lead to the repetition of example parts and, eventually, induce design fixation.

FINAL CONCLUSIONS

According to our results, there are not many striking differences between the novice and expert designers regarding their choices on the most influencing stimuli for idea generation. Novices and experts choose a similar range of material sources, which can be an indicator that if there are differences regarding their performance, it must be dependent on how information is retrieved and processed. To conclude, these findings can derive implications for design education, as they unveil two important factors. First, designers may be creating barriers for their own creativity, due their own choice of material sources. Second, if the range of preferred stimuli is not different between novice and expert designers, their contrasting performances can be due to the distinct cognitive processing. Therefore, a creative outcome does not depend solely on the

frequency and with which variation certain sources of inspiration are used but rather how the stimuli are transformed to generate innovative solutions.

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